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Modelling Decarbonization Pathways in the Energy Sector of Developing Countries: The Case Study of Nepal

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Executive Summary

This study models least-cost decarbonization pathways for Nepal's energy sector to 2050 using the OSeMOSYS optimization framework. Three scenarios were assessed: Business-as-Usual (BAU), Renewable Diversification (REW), and Net-Zero Emissions (NZE). Results show BAU leads to rising fossil dependence, with emissions climbing from 13.8 Mt in 2022 to 24.5 Mt in 2050 and the highest discounted system cost (\approx 84.5 billion USD). REW achieves a \sim 70 % emission cut by 2050 at the lowest cost (\approx 83.1 billion USD) through rapid electrification of cooking and transport, large-scale solar deployment, and industrial fuel switching. NZE reaches full decarbonization by mid-century with only a modest cost premium (\approx 83.8 billion USD). Sectoral interventions in electric cooking, electric buses and two-wheelers, and industrial RDF (Refuse Derived Fuel) derived from Municipal Solid Waste, drive the transition, supported by solar, hydro, and storage expansion. Early renewable investment, binding net-zero targets, and blended-finance mechanisms are critical to secure Nepal's energy future, enhance resilience, and meet its 2045 net-zero commitment.

1. Introduction

Nepal's energy sector is at the heart of its low-carbon development strategy, with the government pledging to cut greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 26.8% by 2035 and achieve net-zero CO₂ by 2045 (GoN 2025). Currently, electricity generation is dominated by hydropower (>90%), yet seasonal variability, floods, and glacial risks threaten system reliability (Energy Sector Synopsis Report 2024). At the same time, demand is expected to triple by 2050 due to widespread electrification of cooking, transport, and industry (Rajbhandari and Limmeechokchai 2022). Despite this, biomass still accounts for a majority share of total energy consumption, while modern renewables such as solar and wind remain marginal (Energy Sector Synopsis Report 2024). Financing constraints further complicate the decarbonization pathway (Jha 2025). The purpose of this study is to model and analyze decarbonization pathways in Nepal's power sector under different scenarios. Its scope extends beyond hydropower to assess diversification through solar, wind, storage, and cross-border trade. The primary objective is to identify cost-effective, resilient, and scalable strategies for achieving Nepal's net-zero targets, while the specific aim is to provide actionable insights for policymakers to balance system reliability, energy security, and climate commitments.

2. Methodology

This study applies OSeMOSYS, a bottom-up linear programming model, to analyze Nepal's long-term decarbonization pathways. The framework determines the least-cost technology mix to satisfy projected electricity demand while adhering to emission targets and resource constraints (Howells et al. 2011). The model was calibrated using national generation, consumption, and trade statistics for 2022–2024, thereby ensuring consistency with observed trends before extending projections to 2050. The research design is comparative: three scenarios (Business-as-Usual (BAU), Accelerated Electrification & RDF Utilization (REW-Diversification), and Net Zero Emission (NZE)) are modeled against each other to highlight system reliability, emissions reduction, and cost trade-offs. Each scenario operationalizes different assumptions regarding technology penetration, financing, and hydro vulnerability, enabling systematic exploration of risks and opportunities.

To transition from data to interpretation, quantitative outputs including capacity expansion, generation mix, costs, and emissions trajectories are assessed against Nepal's NDC 3.0 targets

and the strategic priorities of the Sixteenth Plan. Sensitivity checks are conducted on hydro capacity factors and renewable costs to test model robustness. This step ensures that conclusions are not only technically valid but also policy-relevant. The methodology is summarized in table 1 which explores the assumptions, data source and scenarios briefly.

Figure 1: Scenarios

Table 1: Methodological Framework

Component	Description	Rationale
Data Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NEA Annual Report (2023/24); - WECS Energy Synopsis (2024) ; - NDC 3.0 ; - Sixteenth Plan ; - supplementary finance/economic studies. 	Ensures calibration with official, up-to-date, and policy-relevant data.
Assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electricity demand tripling by 2050 ; - financing need; - hydro vulnerability to climate risks; - technology costs and learning from regional benchmarks. 	Grounds model in plausible long-term projections while incorporating uncertainty.
Scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - BAU: Hydro-dominance, low renewables, dry-season imports. - REW-Diversification: High electrification by 2045 and industrial fuel switching but not full net-zero. 	Enables comparative analysis of resilience, emissions, and cost pathways.

Component	Description	Rationale
	- NZE: REW- Diversification + a binding net-zero cap in 2050	

3. Results and Discussions

The primary energy supply figure below shows a decisive shift in Nepal’s energy mix under the Net-Zero (NZE) pathway compared with both the Business-as-Usual (BAU) and REW-Diversification scenarios. While biomass remains the largest single source across all pathways, its role transforms from traditional use toward modern bioenergy and RDF, supporting cleaner cooking and industrial applications. Fossil fuels such as coal, diesel,

Figure 2: Primary Energy Supply

kerosene, and LPG continue to grow under BAU but decline sharply under NZE, with coal and diesel nearly eliminated by 2045 and gasoline disappearing by 2040, signalling the impact of electrification and strong import and carbon-pricing policies. At the same time, low-carbon sources particularly solar, RDF, and hydropower expand rapidly after 2030, with solar rising from negligible levels to almost 180 PJ by 2050, while hydro steadily increases its share across all scenarios. These results highlight that achieving net-zero emissions requires not only a rapid build-out of renewables and waste-to-energy capacity but also firm regulatory measures to accelerate fossil fuel phase-out and modernize biomass use, ensuring a secure and affordable energy transition.

Targeted interventions in residential cooking as shown in figure 3, road transport in the figure 4, and industrial high-temperature heat as shown in the figure 5 reshape energy demand trajectories across all scenarios. In residential cooking, BAU remains biomass-dominated with LPG rising slowly to 39 PJ by 2050 and no significant electrification. Under NZE, however, a decisive shift occurs: electric cooking grows from near zero to 56 PJ by 2050, displacing LPG completely by mid-century while cutting biomass use to around 352 PJ which is far below the BAU level of over 540 PJ. The REW pathway delivers only partial gains, with limited electrification and continued LPG use. In the transport sector, NZE policy drives deep electrification of buses and two-wheelers. Diesel buses fall from 20 PJ in 2022 to nearly zero after 2046, replaced by electric buses reaching 12.8 PJ by 2050. Gasoline motorcycles decline from 19 PJ to near zero by 2050, while electric motorcycles rise to 5.7 PJ, and electric cars grow modestly to 0.75 PJ as gasoline cars fade. By contrast, BAU sees diesel buses and gasoline motorcycles climb to 36 PJ and 41 PJ, respectively, highlighting the leverage of fleet electrification.

Figure 3: Residential Cooking Consumption

In the industrial high-heat sector, the REW-Diversification and NZE pathways aggressively substitute refuse-derived fuel (RDF) and modern biomass for coal and diesel. RDF, negligible in BAU, scales to ~120 PJ by 2050 (already ~70 PJ by 2035) while coal and diesel demand steadily fall. NZE pushes these trends further, driving fossil inputs close to zero by mid-century. Together these targeted measures lower fossil energy use and boost modern energy across all end uses, with early gains in electric cooking and buses, mid-term momentum from motorcycle electrification

and RDF adoption, and late-decade completion of LPG and diesel bus phase-outs. The sequencing spreads infrastructure costs over time while delivering near-term benefits in import reduction and air-quality improvement, offering a clear, actionable roadmap for policy and investment.

Figure 4: Transport Sector Consumption (Bus/ Car/ Motorcycle)

Figure 5: Industrial High Heat Consumption

The emissions as shown in figure 6 and cost outcomes in figure 7 clearly illustrate the trade-offs between climate ambition and system investment. Decarbonization is not only feasible but also cost-competitive. Under the BAU pathway, total annual emissions climb steadily from about 13.8 Mt in 2022 to nearly 24.5 Mt by 2050, reflecting continued fossil dependence and rising energy demand. By contrast, the REW-Diversification strategy bends the curve downward after

2030, cutting emissions to roughly 7 Mt by 2050, while the NZE pathway achieves a near-complete decarbonization, driving emissions to zero by mid-century. These trajectories demonstrate that early renewable expansion and electrification deliver deep reductions well before 2040, with NZE requiring an even faster post-2035 decline to meet net-zero.

Figure 6: Total Annual Emission

Figure 7: Discounted Annual Emission

Economic results reinforce the feasibility of ambitious action. Although the NZE pathway entails the highest investment (≈ 14.9 billion USD) and slightly higher fixed costs than REW, it compensates through lower variable costs, keeping its discounted total cost (≈ 83.8 billion USD) only marginally above the REW case and still below the BAU cost (≈ 84.5 billion USD). The REW scenario emerges as the least-cost option (≈ 83.1 billion USD) while securing a $\sim 70\%$ emission cut by 2050, demonstrating that deep decarbonization is economically competitive. For policymakers, these results highlight that decisive renewable investments can both curb long-term emissions and avoid higher BAU expenditures, with NZE offering the strongest climate benefits for a modest additional cost premium.

4. Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

Nepal can achieve net-zero by 2050 at competitive cost. Nepal's decarbonization pathways show that a business-as-usual trajectory is neither climate-nor cost-optimal, while both the REW-Diversification and Net-Zero (NZE) scenarios deliver decisive gains in emissions reduction, energy security, and economic efficiency. The REW pathway achieves a $\sim 70\%$ cut in emissions by 2050 at the lowest discounted cost (≈ 83.1 billion USD) through rapid electrification of cooking and transport, large-scale solar deployment, and industrial fuel switching. The NZE scenario drives emissions to net-zero by 2050 with only a marginal cost premium (≈ 83.8 billion USD), proving that full decarbonization is economically viable when combined with early renewable expansion and targeted electrification. Policy priorities should therefore focus on: (i) legally binding net-zero targets to provide investment certainty; (ii) accelerated deployment of solar, storage, and climate-resilient hydropower to diversify beyond seasonal hydro dependence; (iii) sector-specific measures such as clean-cooking programs, electric bus and two-wheeler incentives, and industrial RDF co-firing to displace fossil fuels; and (iv) innovative blended-finance mechanisms and regional power trade to mobilize the USD 77 billion investment need. Acting now to scale renewables, strengthen grids, and enforce carbon-pricing will not only secure Nepal's energy future but also lock in long-term cost savings while aligning with its 2045 net-zero commitment.

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